

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP3 – Determination of drug transfer and infant drug exposure during lactation: generation of quantitative and translatable data

D3.9 Integrated mother-infant PBPK model verified against human lactation data

* *PBPK = physiologically-based pharmacokinetic*

Lead contributors	Julia Macente, Nina Nauwelaerts, Martje Van Neste, Miao-Chan Huang, Karel Allegaert, Anne Smits, Isabelle Huys, Pieter Annaert (7 – KU Leuven)
Other contributors	Rodolfo Hernandez Bonan (20 – BioNotus) Justine Marine Badee (38 – Novartis Pharma AG)

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V1.0	16-03-2024	Summary of integrated mother-infant PBPK models developed for five drugs

1. Contents

Document History.....	1
Abstract.....	3
Glossary	4
1. Introduction.....	5
2. Methods	5
2.1 Adult PBPK models	6
2.2 Lactation PBPK models	7
2.2.1 Infant Dosage Estimation	7
2.3 Infant PBPK models.....	8
2.4 Predictive performance of the PBPK models	8
2.5 Infant Exposure	8
3. Results.....	9
3.1 Adults PBPK models	9
3.2 Lactation PBPK models.....	9
3.3 Infant PBPK models	9
3.4 Infant systemic exposure.....	11
4. Discussion.....	12
5. Conclusion	14
6. References.....	14

Abstract

Introduction: Physiologically-based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modeling emerges as a highly valuable tool to predict the concentrations of drugs in human milk during the lactation phase, as well as to estimate the milk-to-plasma (M/P) ratio of maternal medication, and subsequently, the infant exposure. Work Package 3 (WP3) of ConcePTION aims to generate a non-clinical testing platform to determine drug transfer into human milk and the subsequent exposure of infants.

Aim: The aim of this deliverable is to report the integration of the maternal PBPK model with an infant PBPK model, resulting in a comprehensive maternal-infant PBPK model for the determination of the infant's systemic exposure to maternally administered drugs via human milk, including amoxicillin, cetirizine, levetiracetam, valproic acid, and zidovudine

Methods: The PBPK models were developed in Simcyp® V21 (Certara, L.P., Sheffield, UK) for amoxicillin, levetiracetam, valproic acid, cetirizine, and zidovudine. PBPK models were developed for non-lactating adult healthy volunteers and qualified against *in vivo* clinical data. The verified adult PBPK models were subsequently applied to establish lactation PBPK models using either permeability or perfusion limited models and predicted drug concentrations in human milk. The qualified PBPK model for adults was extrapolated accounting for the physiological changes to establish a PBPK model for a virtual infant population. The daily infant dosage estimated from the lactation PBPK model was used as input to a qualified infant PBPK model, forming the so-called “integrated maternal-infant PBPK model” thus enabling determination of the relative infant systemic exposure compared to the maternal systemic exposure.

Results: The adult PBPK models developed in Simcyp® for the five model drugs adequately described the observed plasma concentration time profiles, as well the PK parameters (*i.e.*, C_{max} and AUC) in non-lactating adult healthy volunteers qualifying as a base model for lactation and pediatrics PBPK models. The lactation PBPK models resulted in an adequate prediction of drug concentration in human milk. The infant PBPK models showed a good prediction of the pharmacokinetic parameters and were able to adequately capture the plasma concentration-time profiles when compared to the *in vivo* clinical data. The integrated maternal-infant PBPK models developed for 5 drugs showed RID values below 5 %, whereas the RID of levetiracetam was estimated to be up to 21%.

Conclusion: The developed PBPK models adequately described the plasma PK of the drugs in adults and infants including human milk concentrations in lactating women. The integration of the qualified infant models with the corresponding lactation PBPK models, revealed a low (<10%) systemic exposure (RIE, %) to maternal medication in breastfed infants *via* human milk for 4 drugs and < 25% for levetiracetam.

Glossary

AUC	Area under the curve
C _{max}	Maximum (or peak) concentration in plasma
GM	Geometric mean
M&S	Modelling and simulation
M/P	Milk-to-Plasma ratio
PBPK	Physiologically-based pharmacokinetic(s)
RID	Relative Infant Dose
RIE	Relative Infant Exposure
VPC	Visual predictive check

1. Introduction

In April 2019, ConcePTION was launched. ConcePTION is a private public partnership that aims to generate information about the use of drugs during pregnancy and breastfeeding: “Building an ecosystem for better monitoring and communicating of medication safety in pregnancy and breastfeeding: validated and regulatory endorsed workflows for fast, optimized evidence generation.” Work Package 3 (WP3) of ConcePTION aims to generate a non-clinical testing platform to determine drug transfer into human milk, and subsequent exposure of infants. While this platform relies on non-clinical methodologies (*i.e.*, *in vivo* animal, *in vitro*, and *in silico*), the predicted outcomes are of clinical relevance (*e.g.*, concentration time profiles of drug in maternal blood and human milk).

According to Wang et al., less than 5% of approved drugs include lactation related data in their labeling[1]. This lack of information presents a significant challenge for breastfeeding mothers, who often face the difficult decision of balancing therapeutic treatment with the desire to continue breastfeeding, especially considering the recognized benefits of breastfeeding. Therefore, generating information regarding use and safety of drugs during early life is relevant for the development and labelling of drugs used in this population. In 2019, the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) published guidance for clinical lactation studies[2]. However, ethical considerations typically discourage voluntary and unnecessary exposure of breastfeeding mothers and their newborns/infants[3], [4].

Physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modelling and simulation, is a dynamic mechanistic approach, that associates the drug candidate physicochemical properties and its absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion with system-specific data, clinical trial design and results in plasma (or human milk) concentration-time profiles. By integrating these data, PBPK modeling generates concentration-time profiles in plasma or human milk, enabling simulation of various physiological conditions and accounting for physiological and developmental changes. PBPK modeling emerges as a highly valuable tool to predict the concentrations of drugs in human milk of breastfeeding mothers, as well as to estimate the milk-to-plasma (M/P) ratio of maternal medication, the daily infant dosage (DID), and, subsequently, the infant's systemic exposure [5], [6], [7]

The aim of this deliverable is to report the development and qualification of these maternal-infant PBPK models using Simcyp® software.

2. Methods

The purpose of this modeling and simulation (M&S) project, was to integrate the developed maternal and infant PBPK models for five drugs, namely amoxicillin (AMX), levetiracetam (LEV), valproic acid (VPA), cetirizine (CET) and zidovudine (ZDV). The models were developed using the Simcyp simulator version 21 (Simcyp 21.1, Certara Inc, Sheffield, UK). The present report provides the general M&S approaches (and underlying assumptions). The *in vivo* clinical observed data in humans for all drugs were obtained from selected literature sources, and the data were extracted using WebPlotDigitizer® version 4.4. The general workflow used to develop the maternal-infant PBPK models is described in Figure 1.

Figure 1- General Workflow of PBPK model development in adult healthy volunteers, lactating women and infants. The training dataset, containing studies after single intravenous (iv) or oral administration, was used to develop the adult PBPK models. At this stage, if necessary, parameter estimation was performed to fit the model prediction to the observed data. A second (i.e., verifying) dataset, was used to assess the performance of each compound-specific PBPK model. The verifying dataset contained multiple studies after single or multiple iv and oral administrations. After successful model verification, PBPK models were applied to breastfeeding women to establish a lactation PBPK model and predict drug concentration in human milk as well as estimate the daily infant dosage received via human milk. The adult PBPK model was extrapolated for infant population considering the physiological changes and ontogeny. The lactation PBPK model, if successful in predicting drug concentration in human milk, was used to estimate the daily dosage received by infants via human milk. This estimation was then used as input for a verified infant PBPK model to assess the infant's relative exposure, forming what is known as the 'Integrated maternal-infant PBPK model'.

2.1 Adult PBPK models

For each model drug, a PBPK model was developed in adult non-lactating populations, either adult healthy volunteer or adult patient population. Drug data (i.e., physicochemical and absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) properties) were combined with physiological data-related parameters describing the specific population to simulate the pharmacokinetics profile of a drug in a healthy adult volunteer. A first set of observed data in healthy volunteers (i.e., a training dataset) was used to build the model. If necessary, parameters were estimated to fit the model prediction to the observed data, implying the so-called middle-out approach. The predictive performance of the model was then evaluated with a second dataset (verification dataset). Virtual populations were composed to closely match the enrolled individuals in the respective *in vivo* clinical trials, when available, with regard to dosing regimen, route of administration, gender ratio, and age. In the absence of information on these parameters, for adult healthy volunteers the default age range of 20-50 years old and female proportion of 0.5 were used.

2.2 Lactation PBPK models

After the development and evaluation of the adult model, the built-in lactation module from Simcyp was selected for the development of lactation PBPK model. The module provides two different approaches. The first type (*i.e.*, the so-called perfusion-limited model) assumes that there is a rapid equilibrium between plasma and human milk. This implies that the concentration of a drug in human milk can be calculated based on the plasma concentration and the milk-to-plasma ratio (M/P ratio). The M/P ratio was calculated based on physicochemical properties (*i.e.*, pH partitioning, protein binding, and distribution into milk lipid), assuming that only the unbound and unionized molecular species will cross the blood-milk barrier, one example of this model is the log-transformed phase distribution model by Atkinson & Begg (1990) [8], [9]. The second approach is the permeability-limited model. The sub-compartment of breast tissue implemented in Simcyp® has a three-compartment structure, consisting of extracellular, intracellular, and milk compartments and includes options to allow total unbound or only unbound unionized molecules to permeate through the blood-milk barrier. For the permeability model, the transfer of medicines to human milk and reuptake from human milk were parametrized by the secretion (CL_{sec}) and reuptake (CL_{re}) clearance as defined by Koshimichi et al. (2011)[10]. A sample size of 100 female subjects at three months postpartum (*i.e.*, aged between 30 to 30.3 years old, weight 65.78 kg) was used in each simulation of the virtual lactation population. For each simulation, the administration protocol was adapted to the clinical study designs reported in literature.

2.2.1 Infant Dosage Estimation

PBPK simulations at steady-state were carried out to predict the daily infant dosage (DID), at the therapeutic dosing regimen for each drug. The dose received *via* human breast milk to the infant (*i.e.*, DID, mL/kg/day) was calculated based on the predicted average concentration in human milk ($C_{average,milk}$ described in Equation 1), and the volume of infant daily milk intake, and described in Equation 2. For safety risk assessment purposes, two scenarios were considered: *i*) a daily milk intake of 150 mL/kg/day and *ii*) an assumed daily milk intake of 200 mL/kg/day[2], [11]. Subsequently, the DID was compared with the maternal dosage for the evaluation of the relative infant dose (RID, %), as described in Equation 3.

$$C_{average,milk} \left(\frac{mg}{L} \right) = \frac{AUC_{milk}}{\tau} \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

$$\text{Daily infant dosage} \left(\frac{mg}{kg \cdot day} \right) = C_{average,milk} \times \text{volume of milk intake (mL)} \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

$$\text{Relative infant dose (RID, \%)} = \frac{\text{Infant dosage (mg/kg/day)}}{\text{Maternal dosage (mg/kg/day)}} \times 100\% \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

Where: AUC: area under the curve, τ is dosing interval The maternal dose in Equation 3 was normalized to the body weight of a virtual lactating population aged between 30 to 30.3 years old, with a mean weight of 65.78 kg (Simcyp® V21).

Additionally, to assess the drug intake during the breastfeeding period, a comparison between the estimated daily infant dosage and the daily therapeutic dosage of the drug in infants, when available, can be evaluated for risk assessment by calculating the relative therapeutic infant dose (RID_{therapeutic} %), according to Equation 4.

$$\text{Relative therapeutic infant dose (RID}_{\text{therapeutic}} \text{, \%)} = \frac{\text{Daily infant dosage (mg/kg/day)}}{\text{Daily therapeutic infant dosage (mg/kg/day)}} \times 100\% \text{ (Equation 4)}$$

2.3 Infant PBPK models

PBPK models for AMX, LEV, VPA, CET and ZDV were developed to simulate the exposure of drugs in infants using Simcyp® paediatric simulator, by incorporating anatomical and physiological changes with age as well as the ontogeny of clearance pathways of each drug. Clinical data from literature were collected for infants aged from 3 months to 1 year old for each drug. Virtual populations were selected to closely match the enrolled individuals in the respective *in vivo* clinical trials, when available, with regards to dosing regimen, route of administration, gender ratio, and age. Information regarding the PK study design, as well as the individual weight and dosing regimen for each infant were often missing. However, when such information was missing, the models were developed based on the average dose reported for the infant population. The doses administered were often reported in “mg/kg”, and if specific weight information was not available, the parameter was assumed based on the typical weight for the specific age range mentioned in each study. The data aligned closely with the average weight reported in the literature, suggesting consistency with the study's overall findings. More information about the model development and qualification can be found in the drug-specific reports, which are available upon request.

2.4 Predictive performance of the PBPK models

The qualification of the predictive performance of the developed PBPK models was evaluated by comparing the predicted plasma concentration-time profiles against the available clinical observed data reported in literature. The PBPK model was accepted when the primary PK parameters (*i.e.*, the maximum plasma concentration (C_{max}) and area under the curve (AUC) were within a 2-fold error margin, as outlined by the European Medicines Agency in 2018 and Food and Drug Administration in 2020 [12], [13].

2.5 Infant Exposure

The verified PBPK models in pediatrics were used to predict the plasma concentration profile in virtual infants (28 days to 3 months old) and then compared to the maternal plasma exposure to evaluate the relative infant exposure (RIE, %) (Equation 5). The daily infant dosage previously calculated was used as input in a verified infant PBPK model. The DID was divided by the dose per feeding, assuming that the infant is breastfed an average of 7.7 times per day, as reported by Yeung et al., 2020[14]. Simulations of the infant PBPK model were performed until steady-state was reached (after at least 5 half-lives), and the AUC_{T-24h} over maternal AUC_{T-24h} was calculated to estimate the RIE (%).

$$\text{Relative infant exposure (RIE, \%)} = \frac{\text{AUC}_{\text{T-24h}} \text{ infant}}{\text{AUC}_{\text{T-24h}} \text{ maternal}} \times 100\% \text{ (Equation 5)}$$

3. Results

3.1 Adults PBPK models

PBPK models were developed, reproduced, or adapted from literature for AMX, LEV, VPA, CET, and ZDV [15], [16], [17] and qualified against *in vivo* clinical data available in literature for adult healthy volunteers and/or patients using Simcyp software. The PBPK models were able to adequately capture the plasma concentration-time profiles as well as the descriptive PK parameters (*i.e.*, C_{\max} and AUC) in adult healthy volunteers after oral, intravenous and single/multiple doses administration at different dose levels. The simulated and observed AUC_{0-t} and C_{\max} values of AMX, LEV, VPA, CET, and ZDV were between 2-fold margin (see Figure 2). More information about the model development and qualification can be found in the drug-specific reports, which are available upon request.

3.2 Lactation PBPK models

The qualified adult PBPK models were used to establish a PBPK model for lactating women, using the Simcyp built-in lactation module (*i.e.*, perfusion or permeability-rate limited model; v21). The lactation PBPK models established for AMX, LEV, VPA, CET and ZDV were in agreement with the simulated plasma or human milk concentration profile when overlapped with the available *in vivo* clinical data. Most of the *in vivo* clinical data were within the 90% confidence interval. The predicted milk-to-plasma ratio are shown in Table 1. More information about model development and evaluation can be found in the corresponding drug-specific reports.

3.3 Infant PBPK models

For each model drug, the developed adult model was extrapolated to the infant population as described in the methods section. The infant PBPK models adequately predicted the observed plasma concentration-time profiles of AMX, LEV, VPA, CET and ZDV. The PBPK models for the infant population showed that most of the observations were within the 5th to 95th percentile predicted concentrations. The simulated and observed AUC and C_{\max} values of AMX, LEV, VPA, CET and ZDV were within 2-fold margin (see Figure 3).

Figure 2- Predictive performance plots of the PBPK models comparing predicted and observed C_{max} and AUC in healthy adults at different dose levels. Symbols represent the clinical data used for model development and model verification. Solid bold line represents the line of unity, dashed lines and solid lines represent the 2.0-fold and 1.5-fold deviation from unity, respectively.

Figure 3- Predictive performance plots of the PBPK models comparing predicted and observed C_{max} and AUC in infant population at different dose levels. Symbols represent the clinical data used for model development and model verification. Solid bold line represents the line of unity, dashed lines and solid lines represent the 2.0-fold and 1.5-fold deviation from unity, respectively.

3.4 Infant systemic exposure

A virtual infant (28 days to 3 months) population was created and used to simulate concentration time profiles for each drug, and simulations at steady-state were carried out with the estimated dose per feed (DID/7.7 feedings per day). Infant over maternal plasma AUC ratio was used to evaluate the relative infant exposure (RIE, %). The DID predicted within the lactation model, as well as the relative infant exposure, can be found in Table 1.

Table 1- Simulated pharmacokinetics parameters in milk and the respectively daily Infant dosage (DID, mg/kg/day), relative infant dose (RID, %) and the relative infant exposure (RIE, %).

	Amoxicillin	Levetiracetam	Valproic Acid	Cetirizine	Zidovudine
M/P ratio	0.14	1.37	0.05	0.16	1.3
C _{avg,milk}	0.66 (0.39-1.04)	47.44 (31.34-68.46)	4.13 (2.70-6.22)	0.025 (0.019-0.033)	0.57 (0.34-1.00)
150 mL human milk intake					
DID (mg/kg/day)	0.10 (0.06-0.16)	7.12 (4.70-10.27)	0.62 (0.41-0.93)	0.0037 (0.0028-0.0050)	0.09 (0.05-0.15)
RID, %	0.21	15.60	1.94	2.95	0.94
RIE, %	0.26 (0.18-0.21)	18.13 (12.30-26.70)	5.48 (3.46-8.09)	2.55 (1.94-3.39)	1.33 (0.86-2.67)
200 mL human milk intake					
DID (mg/kg/day)	0.13 (0.08-0.21)	9.49 (6.27-13.69)	0.83 (0.54-1.24)	0.005 (0.0038-0.0067)	0.11 (0.07-0.20)
RID, %	0.29	20.80	2.59	3.29	1.25
RIE, %	0.34 (0.28-0.55)	24.24 (15.97-35.08)	7.44 (4.81-10.61)	3.39 (2.60-4.60)	1.33 (1.20-3.98)

DID: Daily Infant Dosage; M/P: milk-to-plasma ratio; RID; Relative Infant Dose, results are given based on the geometric mean values of the daily infant dosage over the maternal dosage; RIE: Relative Infant Exposure; results are given in geometric mean (5th percentile; 95th percentile).

The daily infant dose was compared to the recommended therapeutic dosage for pediatrics, when available (Table 2).

Table 2- Predicted daily infant dosage as a percentage of the pediatric therapeutic dose.

Drug	Therapeutic Dosage Used as reference (mg/kg/day)	RID _{therapeutic} (%) assuming 150 mL milk intake	RID _{therapeutic} (%) assuming 200 mL milk intake
Amoxicillin	50	0.20	0.26
Levetiracetam	40	17.80	23.73
Valproic Acid	40	1.55	2.08
Cetirizine	0.5	0.75	1.00
Zidovudine	24	0.38	0.46

DID: Daily Infant Dosage; RID: relative infant dose.

4. Discussion

The objective of this deliverable was to report the development and qualification of the maternal-infant PBPK model using Simcyp software to predict the infant drug systemic exposure *via* human milk intake after maternal oral administration of amoxicillin, levetiracetam, valproic acid, cetirizine, and zidovudine.

Non-lactating adults healthy volunteers models were developed and evaluated based on their ability to predict the plasma concentrations after oral or intravenous administration of the drugs. The models adequately captured the plasma concentration-time profiles as well as the primary PK parameters (*i.e.*, C_{max} and AUC_{0-t} , < 2-fold bias). This suggested that the PBPK models was qualified as a base models to build PBPK model for lactating women and subsequent extrapolation to pediatrics population.

The evaluated adult PBPK models were used to establish lactation PBPK models, considering the physiological differences of a lactating women. Two different approaches were applied to estimate the drug transfer in human milk. For amoxicillin, levetiracetam, cetirizine, and zidovudine, the permeability-limited milk distribution concept incorporated the drug transfer into human milk, by relying on the bidirectional clearance (CL) values between blood and milk. These CL values were calculated based on the Quantitative Structure Property Relationship algorithm developed by Koshimichi and collaborators. This approach is consistent with the recent strategies for lactation PBPK model building published by Nauwelaerts et al., 2023 [3]. For valproic acid, a minimal PBPK model was developed, with a single-adjustment compartment ('SAC') to describe the distribution[18]. In case of a minimal PBPK model, the Simcyp lactation module is available only for perfusion-limited milk distribution. For perfusion-limited models, the M/P ratio values were calculated using the log-transformed phase distribution model [6], [19] and used as input to predict drug concentrations in human milk, *i.e.* assuming almost instantaneous drug milk distribution.

The predictions were compared with the available *in vivo* clinical data in the literature. Most of the *in vivo* clinical data were within the 90% confidence interval of predictions. The M/P ratio predicted by the lactation PBPK model showed good agreement with the M/P ratio reported in the literature. This agreement allowed for the estimation of the daily infant dosage (DID) and the relative infant dosage (RID) of the selected drugs. Data are available in the drug-specific report, which can be provided upon request

Following the proposed workflow, the same qualified adult models were used to extrapolate to infant model for determining the plasma concentration-time profile in infant populations for each drug using a virtual pediatric population with the Simcyp simulator. This accounted for age-related anatomical and physiological processes, as well as incorporating ontogeny profiles for ADME relevant proteins. The infant PBPK models exhibited good prediction accuracy (without estimation or fitting of parameters) when compared to observed clinical data reported in the literature.

The daily infant dosage determined previously was used as the dosing regimen in the evaluated infant PBPK model to assess the infant systemic exposure based on the infant AUC over maternal AUC over 24h at steady-state.

Often, breastfeeding mothers need to continue drug therapeutic treatment, and a major issue to take into consideration is the lack of information regarding the clinical risk to the breastfed infant. The lactation PBPK model allows the estimation of an important risk assessment parameter based on the percentage of weight-adjusted maternal and infant dosage: the relative infant dose (RID, %). Lactation PBPK models can serve as a first step in estimating daily infant dosage and relative infant dose to inform drug safety in breastfed infants. The appropriate threshold to be considered when evaluating these results is still under debate. Some authors suggest that a 10% RID can be considered a safety threshold in risk assessment, while an RID higher than 25% should be avoided by breastfeeding mothers [4], [5], [20], [21].

The RID was <5% for all drugs, except for levetiracetam, which revealed an RID of 16-21%. This result indicated that levetiracetam has a relatively higher transfer rate into human milk. In literature, the infant serum level is reported to average 14% of the maternal serum levels[22].

The ADME processes in infants are influenced by physiological maturation and ontogeny. As infants progress through developmental stages, changes in organ function, enzyme activity, and transporter expression affect how drugs are absorbed, distributed, metabolized, and excretion. Ontogeny plays a crucial role in determining drug exposure and therapeutic efficacy, emphasizing the need to understand developmental pharmacokinetics to ensure drug safety for neonates and infants. The integration of the verified maternal and infant PBPK models allows for the assessment of another critical index, the relative infant exposure (RIE, %), which provides valuable information for evaluating infant risk following maternal drug intake. Levetiracetam was the only drug to show a relative infant exposure greater than 10%, with an RIE ranging from 18%-24%.

Additionally, as recommended in regulatory guidelines [2], we compared the estimated daily infant dosage to the pediatric therapeutic dose ($RID_{\text{therapeutic}}$). The $RID_{\text{therapeutic}}$ values (Table 2) were less than 25% compared to the dosing used for pediatric therapeutic treatment, indicating (relatively) low risk of therapeutic effects in infants.

As discussed in the Deliverable D3.8 “Individual PBPK model for predicting exposure of infants to selected drugs” and part of an ongoing WP3 (Task 3.5) efforts, the infant PBPK models will be optimized by integrating further information related to the specific physiological aspects of the exclusively breastfed infant. Furthermore, differences in the maturational physiology of infants fed human milk or formula milk have been described regarding the growth, fat mass, and lean mass of infants. For instance, breastfed infants take longer to recover their birth weight after initial weight loss in the first days of life [23]. A systematic search has been conducted in the literature to collect the maturational physiology of infants fed human milk. This data will be implemented in PBPK software as an exclusively breastfed infant population. PBPK models developed for this special population with these data, will allow us to make more accurate predictions of drug exposure in exclusively breastfed

infants and the drug transfer through human milk after maternal drug intake.

Sensitivity analyses will be performed to assess the impact of the changes in specific physiological parameters unique to breastfed infants (*e.g.*, human milk composition: fat content, protein content) and human milk intake rate) on drug exposure in breastfed infants. These analyses can lead to a better understanding of how variations in breastfeeding-related factors affect drug levels in infants.

The lactation PBPK models were developed based on physicochemical properties (semi-mechanistic models) to predict the drug concentration in human milk. As a next step to refine and improve the lactation PBPK models, *in vitro* permeability coefficient data will be implemented as part of WP3 work. The integrated maternal-infant model provides a better understanding of the drug transfer after maternal intake through human milk and consequently the infant's drug systemic exposure. The daily infant dose *via* breastfeeding was used as the dosing regimen for the infant PBPK model and allowed the determination of the relative infant exposure.

5. Conclusion

Overall, the herein presented data showed a good prediction of the plasma concentration-time profiles of amoxicillin, levetiracetam, valproic acid, cetirizine, and zidovudine in adults and pediatrics, including human milk concentrations in lactating women. The incorporation of the qualified maternal-infant PBPK model resulted in a comprehensive evaluation of the systemic exposure in breastfed infants via human milk.

6. References

- [1] J. Wang *et al.*, "Evaluation of the Safety of Drugs and Biological Products Used During Lactation: Workshop Summary," *Clin Pharmacol Ther*, vol. 101, no. 6, pp. 736–744, Jun. 2017, doi: 10.1002/cpt.676.
- [2] Fda, Cder, and Mccrayk, "Clinical Lactation Studies: Considerations for Study Design Guidance for Industry DRAFT GUIDANCE." [Online]. Available: <https://www.fda.gov/Drugs/GuidanceComplianceRegulatoryInformation/Guidances/default.htm>
- [3] N. Nauwelaerts *et al.*, "Generic Workflow to Predict Medicine Concentrations in Human Milk Using Physiologically-Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) Modelling—A Contribution from the ConcePTION Project," *Pharmaceutics*, vol. 15, no. 5, May 2023, doi: 10.3390/pharmaceutics15051469.
- [4] R. H. J. Verstegen, P. O. Anderson, and S. Ito, "Infant drug exposure via breast milk," *Br J Clin Pharmacol*, vol. 88, no. 10, pp. 4311–4327, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1111/bcp.14538.
- [5] S. R. Delaney, P. R. V. Malik, C. Stefan, A. N. Edginton, D. A. Colantonio, and S. Ito, "Predicting Escitalopram Exposure to Breastfeeding Infants: Integrating Analytical and In Silico Techniques," *Clin Pharmacokinet*, vol. 57, no. 12, pp. 1603–1611, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1007/s40262-018-0657-2.
- [6] A. Pansari, M. Faisal, M. Jamei, and K. Abduljalil, "Prediction of basic drug exposure in milk using a lactation model algorithm integrated within a physiologically based pharmacokinetic model," *Biopharm Drug Dispos*, vol. 43, no. 5, pp. 201–212, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1002/bdd.2334.
- [7] K. Abduljalil, A. Pansari, J. Ning, and M. Jamei, "Prediction of drug concentrations in milk during breastfeeding, integrating predictive algorithms within a physiologically-based pharmacokinetic model," *CPT Pharmacometrics Syst Pharmacol*, vol. 10, no. 8, pp. 878–889, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1002/psp4.12662.
- [8] U. C. Atkinson and E. J. Begg, "Prediction of Drug Distribution into Human Milk from

- Physicochemical Characteristics,” *Clin Pharmacokinet*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 151–167, 1990, doi: 10.2165/00003088-199018020-00005.
- [9] E. J. Begg and H. C. ATKINSONt, “MODELLING OF THE PASSAGE OF DRUGS INTO MILK,” 1993.
- [10] H. Koshimichi, K. Ito, A. Hisaka, M. Honma, and H. Suzuki, “Analysis and Prediction of Drug Transfer into Human Milk Taking into Consideration Secretion and Reuptake Clearances across the Mammary Epithelia,” *Drug Metabolism and Disposition*, vol. 39, no. 12, pp. 2370–2380, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1124/dmd.111.040972.
- [11] L. Cloostermans, K. Allegaert, A. Smits, and M. Van Neste, “The Deuterium Oxide Dilution Method to Quantify Human Milk Intake Volume of Infants: A Systematic Review—A Contribution from the ConcePTION Project,” *Nutrients*, vol. 16, no. 23, p. 4205, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.3390/nu16234205.
- [12] Green and Dionna, “Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic Analyses — Format and Content Guidance for Industry,” 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.fda.gov/Drugs/GuidanceComplianceRegulatoryInformation/Guidances/default.htm>
- [13] E. Medicines Agency, “Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (CHMP) Guideline on the reporting of physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modelling and simulation,” 2018. [Online]. Available: www.ema.europa.eu/contact
- [14] C. H. T. Yeung, S. Fong, P. R. V. Malik, and A. N. Edginton, “Quantifying breast milk intake by term and preterm infants for input into paediatric physiologically based pharmacokinetic models,” Apr. 01, 2020, *Blackwell Publishing Ltd*. doi: 10.1111/mcn.12938.
- [15] K. Abduljalil, J. Ning, A. Pansari, X. Pan, and M. Jamei, “Prediction of Maternal and Fetoplacental Concentrations of Cefazolin, Cefuroxime, and Amoxicillin during Pregnancy Using Bottom-Up Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic Models,” *Drug Metabolism and Disposition*, vol. 50, no. 4, pp. 386–400, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1124/dmd.121.000711.
- [16] T. M. Conner, R. C. Reed, and T. Zhang, “A Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic Model for Optimally Profiling Lamotrigine Disposition and Drug–Drug Interactions,” *Eur J Drug Metab Pharmacokinet*, vol. 44, no. 3, pp. 389–408, 2019, doi: 10.1007/s13318-018-0532-4.
- [17] F. Salem, B. G. Small, and T. N. Johnson, “Development and application of a pediatric mechanistic kidney model,” *CPT Pharmacometrics Syst Pharmacol*, vol. 11, no. 7, pp. 854–866, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.1002/psp4.12798.
- [18] T. M. Conner *et al.*, “Physiologically based pharmacokinetic modeling of disposition and drug–drug interactions for valproic acid and divalproex,” *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, vol. 111, pp. 465–481, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.ejps.2017.10.009.
- [19] H. C. Atkinson and E. J. Begg, “Prediction of Drug Distribution into Human Milk from Physicochemical Characteristics,” *Clin Pharmacokinet*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 151–167, Feb. 1990, doi: 10.2165/00003088-199018020-00005.
- [20] P. Anderson and J. Sauberan, “Modeling drug passage into human milk,” *Clin Pharmacol Ther*, vol. 100, no. 1, pp. 42–52, Jul. 2016, doi: 10.1002/cpt.377.
- [21] X. Pan and K. Rowland Yeo, “Addressing drug safety of maternal therapy during breastfeeding using <scp>physiologically-based pharmacokinetic</scp> modeling,” *CPT Pharmacometrics Syst Pharmacol*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 535–539, May 2022, doi: 10.1002/psp4.12802.
- [22] I. Kacirova, M. Grundmann, and H. Brozmanova, “Umbilical cord, maternal milk and breastfed infant levetiracetam concentrations monitoring at delivery and during early postpartum period,” *Pharmaceutics*, vol. 13, no. 3, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.3390/pharmaceutics13030398.
- [23] P. D. Macdonald, S. R. M. Ross, L. Grant, and D. Young, “Neonatal weight loss in breast and formula fed infants,” *Arch Dis Child Fetal Neonatal Ed*, vol. 88, no. 6, 2003, doi: 10.1136/fn.88.6.f472.